

Speculation on the Conservation of Momentum and Spatial Invariance

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 27, 2024

It is well-known that the quantum mechanical free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with momentum conservation from: $\int \exp(-i(p_1+p_2) \cdot r) \exp(i(p_3+p_4) \cdot r) dr \text{ vector} = 0$ unless $p_1+p_2 \text{ vector} = p_3+p_4 \text{ vector}$. In this note, we try to examine why this conservation is expected to arise from a probabilistic picture. We argue that the form $\exp(-ipx)$ does not simply arise from the insistence that the classical probability $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length, contain both p and $-p$. A real function may yield this result. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ breaks the notion of locality by introducing a wavelength region, but then creates spatial invariance on average by having equally sized crests and troughs. Thus, due to this nonlocality, one must perform integrals over a wavelength to see that: $\int dx \exp(-ip_2x)\exp(ip_1x) = 0$ for $p_1 \neq p_2$. The wavelength is that associated with $-p_2+p_1$. Thus, we stress the importance of "i".

We then try to link this notion of creating a $P(x) = \text{constant}$ as the only integrable probability to momentum conservation. We then note that an x -biased function could allow for momentum transitions and argue that this function is $V(x)$, a spatial potential. Thus, we argue from momentum conservation reasons which follow from the $P(x) = \text{constant}$ notion, that $\int \exp(-ip_2x) V(x) \exp(ip_1x) dx$ can yield information about momentum transitions.

Conservation of Momentum and Its Association with Probability

The idea of conservation of momentum exists in Newtonian mechanics and is not associated with probability, but with force. Newton's second law: $\text{Force} = dp/dt$ suggests that if the net force is 0 the dp/dt is 0 and so p , momentum is conserved. Newton also advocates action-reaction which leads to a net force of zero. As a result, conservation of momentum is not directly linked to spatial probability distributions.

It is known from an ideal gas that in the absence of a potential $V(x)$, density is constant throughout the volume and this is linked with constant pressure, which is linked to force. Thus, classical statistical mechanics links a spatial distribution with pressure/force. In the ideal gas there is equal probability for p and $-p$ and so a kind of conservation of net 0 momentum at each x .

We suggest that this idea of spatial invariance which appears in an ideal gas, is also present for constant momentum/velocity for a single particle. In such a case, there is no equilibrium of many particles, but a constant velocity implies the same time dt is spent in each equal dx . A probability, however, represents a situation with bias removed and motion in one direction implies bias. Thus, for a single particle $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length, that one must have p and $-p$ together. This implies that:

$$P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x) = P(x) = \text{constant} \quad \text{where } P_d(p,x) \text{ is a dynamic probability ((1))}$$

Thus, p and $-p$ must cancel and through this cancellation also remove x from ((1)). One could in principle have:

$$Pd(p,x) = a_1 \text{ power } f(\text{odd})(p) * a_2 \text{ power } g(\text{odd})(x) \quad ((2)) \text{ to achieve } ((1))$$

A function $g(\text{odd})(x)$, however, assumes bias in x if one does not have: $g(x)=x$ ((2)). For spatial invariance, one cannot have such a bias in x .

One may notice at this point that $g(\text{odd})(x)$ and $f(\text{odd})(p)$ are real functions. This introduces bias because probability grows or decreases indefinitely, but we defer this issue to the next section because the remedy, i.e. $x \rightarrow ix$ has serious physical consequences as well as being the driver for momentum conservation, we argue.

One may note that physically the odd function $|p|$, i.e. p magnitude, is linked to the magnitude of an impulse if p strikes a target. Choosing $f(\text{odd})(p) = p$ ((3)) would then seem to be linked to Newton's net force=0 scenario. This seems to also be in keeping with an information picture in which $px = \ln(Pd(p,x))$ is considered to be information. We suggest that information should be related to physically important information. One could, however, argue that $ppp = (p)(pp)$ where the first p is linked to momentum and (pp) to nonrelativistic kinetic energy etc. Given p , however, one can create the energy expression (both relativistically with m_0 known and nonrelativistically). Thus, it seems that choosing $f(\text{odd})(p)=p$ is in keeping with Newton's notion of force and using $-p, p$ with action-reaction. As a result, ((1)) is equivalent to:

$$\exp(ipx) = Pd(p,x) \quad ((3))$$

It is possible, however, to obtain ((3)) with no notion of force or impulse. One may simply suggest that:

$$Pd(p_1,x) Pd(p_2,x) = Pd(p_1+p_2,x) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is an AND probability scenario. This also leads to a $f(\text{odd})(p)=p$ (one dimension, $p \cdot r$ in 3-dimensions.)

((4)) has important consequences, we argue, because $Pd(-p,x)Pd(p,x)=\text{constant}$, but $-p_1$ with p_2 does not if $p_1 \neq p_2$. In such a case, the product is biased or directional, in fact it is given by ((4)). Thus, $Pd(p_1,x)$ is no longer a solution constrained by $P(x)=\text{constant}$ which is the initial constraint. We suggest that there must be a remedy to this which we examine in the next section.

Arguments for $Pd(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$

In the above section, we argued that $f(\text{odd})(p)=p$ on the basis of p 's link with impulse and Newtonian force or on ((4)). We now wish to consider some further considerations which we argue are important.

In the above section, $Pd(p,x)$ is considered to be positive as probabilities are in classical probability theory. We noted that this leads to a growing or decreasing probability which leads to

bias in x . $P(x) = \text{constant}$ suggests no bias, but we argue that there must be some bias in $P_d(p,x)$ because it represents motion in one direction. The question is then: How much bias does one allow? If one does not permit $P_d(p,x)$ to grow or decrease indefinitely then it seems that one must introduce periodicity, i.e.

$$g(\text{odd})(x) = x \rightarrow ix \quad ((5))$$

((5)) does not remove bias, but it deals with it in a special way we argue because one has:

$$P_d(x,p) = \exp(i p x) \quad ((6))$$

We suggest that it is not just the case that one has two periodic functions, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, but that each may take on positive and negative values. Thus, the bias for a directional p means that one has a fixed biased length region, the wavelength \hbar/p , and in this region, for both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, a probability hump comes at the expense of a probability trough, just like in a physical wave (e.g.. water wave). We suggest that this has important consequences and essentially follows from using "i", i.e. periodicity. The point we make is that it is this "i" and the equal hump-trough areas which ensure that only the integral of $P_d(-p,x)P_d(p,x) = \text{constant}$ does not vanish. In other words, $P_d(p,x)$ really is directly associated with the classical probability $P(x) = \text{constant}$ because $\int P(x) dx = 1$ whereas:

$$\int dx P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x) = 0 \text{ for } p \neq -p \quad ((7))$$

In other words, the bias of directional p only exists within a wavelength region and is 0 averaged over this region (i.e. P_d integration).

To see the importance of positive and negative values of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, we first consider a function $A(px) + i B(px)$ where $A(x) > 0$ and $B(x) > 0$ are both periodic in px and B is a shifted A . In such a case, ((4)) yields:

$$\text{Real part of ((4)) for } p_1 = p \text{ and } p_2 = p \rightarrow A(px)A(px) - B(px)B(px) \quad ((8))$$

((8)) can be negative in regions if B is an x -shifted version of A , but this contradicts the assumption that $A > 0$ and $B > 0$. Thus, A and B are both negative and positive. There is bias in a wavelength region, but it averages out to give the appearance of spatial invariance.

Consequences for Conservation of Momentum

The above arguments seem to be independent of the Newtonian concept of conservation of momentum. We argued that for $P(x) = \text{constant}$ one needs p AND $-p$ at each x point. $P_d(p,x)$ and $P_d(-p,x)$ are both associated with crest-trough bias within a wavelength, but compensate each other to create a constant when multiplied. This leads to a semblance of an average overall invariance in space.

There still, however, is no notion of conservation of momentum. This notion only seems to appear when one considers:

$$\int dx P_d(-p_1, x) P_d(-p_2, x) P_d(p_3, x) P_d(p_4, x) \quad ((9))$$

The integral ((9)) is a generalization of $P_d(-p, x) P_d(p, x)$.

By the arguments above, especially the use of "i" to create the best possible spatial translational invariance, one sees that ((9)) is zero unless: $p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4$, i.e. conservation of momentum occurs. In other words, one requires $P(x) = \text{constant}$ to have classical spatial invariance and if the P_d 's in question do not conserve momentum, the resulting probability ((9)), although it exists, integrates to zero. Thus, the use of "i", i.e. a periodic cycling which has equal positive crests and negative troughs seems to be responsible for conservation of momentum in the probabilistic picture. It is "i" which ensures that $\exp(ipx)$ is not any solution of $P_d(p, x) P_d(-p, x) = \text{constant} = P(x)$, but a special one which although it has bias within a wavelength region, ensures that the average bias (i.e. integral of $P_d(p, x) dx$ over a wavelength) is 0. Thus, if there is no bias function such as a potential $V(x)$, one requires $P_d(-p, x) P_d(p, x)$ in order to obtain an integrand which does not integrate to 0.

As a result, if there are momentum changing forces in space, there is a potential $V(x)$ which creates bias in space. If this potential or a function of it were added as a factor in ((9)), one could have changes in momentum, i.e. $p_1 + p_2$ would not need to equal $p_3 + p_4$.

If momentum changes then ((4)) suggests $n(V(x))$, where n is an unknown function, should be broken into $\exp(ikx)$ summands. Physically, we have argued that p is proportional to impulse hits and it is known that a potential renders impulse hits as does a force. If one assumes that:

$$V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((10))$$

then for a conservative force: $F = -dV/dx$ or $F(x) = \sum_k k V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((11))$.

k is proportional to impulse hit and to force, so it seems that ((10)) is a reasonable assumption and that $n(V(x)) = V(x)$. Thus, on the basis of momentum conservation alone, one would suggest the form:

$$\int dx \exp(-ip_1 x) V(x) \exp(ip_2 x) \quad ((12))$$

((12)) is written to deal with conservation of momentum, i.e. the desire to create $P(x) = \text{constant}$, but shows different weights for different p_1 values, i.e. different outcomes.

It is ultimately ((12)) squared which yields the Born result, but we suggest that basic ideas are already linked to momentum conservation which in turn is associated with the form $\exp(ipx)$ needed to ensure that only $P(x) = P_d(-p, x) P_d(p, x)$ yields a nonzero dx integral result.

Conclusion

In this note, we try to understand why the quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, is so strongly associated with momentum conservation. We note that $P(x)=\text{constant}$ and insist on $P(x)=P_d(p,x)P(-p,x)$, but one may have real solutions. These show probability bias, i.e. grow or decrease indefinitely, whereas using $\exp(ipx)$ leads to bias within wavelength regions. Furthermore, and importantly, this bias is due to equal size crest-trough regions which integrate to 0. This is important if one wishes $\int P(x)dx = \int P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x)dx$ to survive and other combinations $\int P_d(-p_1,x)P_d(p_2,x) dx = 0$ if $p_1 \neq p_2$. One cannot insist on P_d products being 1 at each x unless one uses p and $-p$ in the two factors due to nonlocal biased wavelength regions, but one can insist on the integral being zero. Thus, we stress the importance of “ i ” in $\exp(ipx)$.

Bias may exist, but only in wavelength long regions of space. This is why one must perform an integral over at least a wavelength, even when using $P_d(-p_1,x)P_d(p_2,x)$. One uses the wavelength associated with $-p_1+p_2$. This suggests the notion of nonlocality which only creates the sense of translational invariance on average.

These ideas may seem to have nothing to do with momentum conservation, but we suggest that only integrals of the form of ((9)) with momentum conservation are nonzero. In other words, it is the “striving” for $P(x)=\text{constant}$, i.e. spatial invariance, which leads to momentum conservation in a probability scenario. ((9)) also shows that if one may find a biased x function, such as $V(x)$ potential, one may have $p_2 \neq p_1$ and find weights for different $p_1 \rightarrow p_2, p_3, p_4$ etc transitions. We argue that $V(x)$ and not $n(V(x))$, where n is an unknown function, suffices based on the idea that p is proportional to impulse.